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Innovation of Teaching Methodology for Improving English Language Skills: Suggestopedia for Teaching Reading and Writing

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Abstract

This study investigates an innovative teaching methodology that combines suggestopedia, digital resources, and experimental and control groups to improve reading-writing English skills. The methodology integrates relaxation and visualization techniques of suggestopedia with engaging digital tools to create a stimulating learning environment. A pre-test established a baseline, and the innovative approach was implemented over several weeks, with lessons integrating suggestopedia and digital resources like multimedia presentations and online reading-writing platforms. A post-test showed statistically significant improvements in students' writing performance. Focus group discussions revealed that students found the lessons engaging, confidence-boosting, and effective in enhancing their reading and writing abilities, particularly appreciating the relaxed atmosphere of suggestopedia and the interactive nature of the digital tools. The study demonstrates the potential of this innovative approach to enhance English writing skills and foster a positive learning experience, warranting further research on its long-term effects and applications in diverse educational contexts.

Keywords: Teaching Methodology, Suggestopedia, Language Skills, Digital Tools

1. Introduction

This article presents the effectiveness of an innovative teaching methodology that incorporates suggestopedia, digital resources, and experimental and control groups to improve the English reading-writing skills of students. Suggestopedia is a teaching method developed by Bulgarian psychotherapist Georgi Lozanov that combines relaxation and visualization techniques to accelerate learning (Lozanov, 2005). The methodology combines the relaxation and visualization techniques of suggestopedia with engaging digital tools to create a stimulating learning

environment. Focus groups were utilized as a research technique to gather qualitative feedback from students on their experiences and perceptions, which is a valuable method for understanding student engagement and satisfaction (Krueger & Casey, 2015).

A pre-test was administered to establish a baseline of students' writing abilities. The innovative methodology was then implemented over a period of several weeks, with lessons integrating suggestopedia and digital resources such as multimedia presentations, online writing platforms, and collaborative editing tools. At the conclusion of the intervention, a post-test was given to measure the development of students' reading and writing skills. The results indicate that the combination of suggestopedia and digital resources had a positive impact on students' reading-writing performance. Scores on the post-test showed statistically significant improvements compared to the pre-test (Merlin & Larekeng, 2018). Experimental group discussions revealed that students found the lessons engaging, confidence-boosting, and effective in enhancing their writing abilities. Participants particularly appreciated the relaxed atmosphere created by suggestopedia and the interactive nature of the digital tools.

This study demonstrates the potential of innovative teaching methodologies that integrate suggestopedia and digital resources to enhance English reading-writing skills. The findings suggest that this approach can lead to measurable improvements in students' reading and writing abilities while also fostering a positive learning experience. Further research is warranted to explore the long-term effects and potential applications of this methodology in diverse educational contexts. The authors' motivation is to provide reliable information about the use of innovative methodologies and didactic and digital resources for the improvement of reading and writing skills in the English language. The authors propose the following research questions:

1. Why suggestopedia is helpful for improving teaching methodology in reading and writing skills?
2. Is the combination of suggestopedia plus digital competencies significantly supportive of boosting Reading-writing English skills?
3. Is the suggestopedia method an effective approach for developing English reading and writing skills?
4. How suggestopedia method can be applied to the development and improvement of English reading and writing skills?

The aim of this study is to ascertain the efficacy of the Suggestopedia methodology in enhancing English language reading and writing abilities.

2. Literature Review

In order to facilitate comprehension of this study, the key concepts are presented below.

2.1 Suggestopedia in the Context of Second Language Acquisition

Suggestopedia, a pedagogical approach developed by Georgi Lozanov, places an emphasis on the employment of relaxation and visualization techniques as a means of facilitating the acquisition of language. This approach is based on the premise that a relaxed state facilitates enhanced learning by allowing students to access their untapped potential (Lozanov, 2005). The efficacy of suggestopedia has been substantiated by empirical evidence in a multitude of educational settings, most notably in the domain of second language acquisition. For example, Colliander and Fejes (2020) investigated the resurgence of suggestopedia in Sweden, emphasizing its efficacy in instructing adult migrants. The study revealed that participants exhibited notable enhancements in their linguistic abilities, attributing this accomplishment to the method's capacity to foster a conducive, low-anxiety learning atmosphere.

Moreover, evidence indicates that suggestopedia is an effective approach for enhancing specific language competencies, such as writing. In a study conducted by Isnaini (2021), the use of suggestopedia was investigated as a potential method for enhancing students' narrative writing abilities. The findings indicated that students who were instructed using the suggestopedia method exhibited significant improvements in their writing abilities in comparison to those who received conventional instruction. This indicates that the method not only facilitates

language acquisition but also enhances specific skills, thereby making it a valuable tool for educators seeking to improve students' overall language proficiency.

In addition to its efficacy, suggestopedia's capacity for adaptation to diverse learner populations renders it a particularly attractive option. In a study conducted by Yuliani (2018), the method was applied to a group of seventh-grade students in Indonesia. The results demonstrated a notable enhancement in the students' writing abilities. This adaptability is of particular importance in the context of today's diverse classrooms, where students originate from a range of linguistic and cultural backgrounds. The favorable results associated with suggestopedia indicate that it can be an effective approach in the teaching of English as a second language, particularly for students who may experience anxiety in traditional learning environments.

2.2 Digital Competencies in the Teaching of Second Languages

The incorporation of digital competencies into language teaching has become a crucial aspect of the contemporary educational landscape. The utilization of digital tools and resources has the potential to enhance the learning experience, facilitating the delivery of interactive and engaging content. In a recent publication, DirectEnglish (2023) delineates the advantages of integrating online platforms into blended English Language Teaching (ELT) programs. These include enhanced student engagement, flexibility, and personalization. The utilization of digital resources enables educators to adapt their instruction to align with the heterogeneous needs of their students, thereby fostering a more inclusive learning environment.

Furthermore, gamification has emerged as an innovative strategy to enhance motivation and engagement among language learners. Burgos et al. (2024) conducted an investigation into the impact of gamification on children's motivation to learn English as a foreign language. The study revealed that the incorporation of game-like elements into language learning resulted in a notable enhancement in students' enthusiasm and participation. This approach has the additional benefit of making the learning process more enjoyable, while also fostering a sense of achievement. This encourages students to take risks and explore the language more freely.

In conjunction with gamification, the cultivation of digital competencies is a crucial aspect of equipping students with the requisite skills to navigate the demands of the 21st century. Mero et al. (2023) highlight the significance of digital competencies in facilitating the development of English language communication skills. The integration of technology into language instruction affords educators the opportunity to provide students with the chance to hone their communication abilities in realistic, meaningful contexts. This not only enhances language proficiency but also provides students with the requisite skills to navigate an increasingly digital world.

2.3 Digital Competencies plus Suggestopedia for enhance writing-reading abilities

The integration of suggestopedia and digital resources offers a promising approach to enhancing students' reading and writing abilities. The combination of multimedia presentations, online writing platforms, and collaborative editing tools with suggestopedia techniques enables educators to create a stimulating learning environment that fosters engagement and creativity (Ansaldi, 2022). Such integration enables students to engage with the material in a variety of ways, thereby enhancing their comprehension and retention of language concepts.

To illustrate, Marleni (2020) demonstrated that the use of technological writing features has the potential to enhance students' writing abilities by providing them with the necessary tools to effectively organize their thoughts and engage in collaborative learning with their peers. As Orellana and Mayorga (2021) have observed, the application of digital storytelling and interactive platforms can facilitate opportunities for students to practice their writing in a supportive and engaging context. This approach has been demonstrated to enhance literacy skills while also encouraging students to express their ideas in a more spontaneous and imaginative manner, thereby improving the overall learning experience.

Additionally, the integration of suggestopedia and digital resources aligns with contemporary educational trends that emphasize student-centered learning. Rodríguez-Pérez (2023) presents a discussion of the potential for digital

resources to enhance communicative competence within the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) education. The combination of suggestopedia and digital tools allows educators to create a comprehensive learning experience that addresses the cognitive, emotional, and social aspects of language acquisition through the incorporation of relaxation techniques. This integrated approach has the potential to result in notable enhancements in students' reading and writing abilities, which may ultimately contribute to a more constructive learning experience.

2.4 An environment conducive to effective teaching and learning

The creation of a positive and supportive learning environment is of paramount importance for effective teaching and learning. The available evidence suggests that a favorable learning environment has a positive impact on student motivation and engagement, which are crucial elements in the acquisition of language skills (Gulo, 2020). A supportive atmosphere encourages students to take risks in their language use, thereby fostering a sense of belonging and community within the classroom. Innovative teaching techniques, such as focus groups, can provide valuable insights into students' experiences and perceptions, thereby enabling educators to adapt their teaching strategies to meet learners' needs (Krueger & Casey, 2015).

Consequently, the implementation of pre-tests and post-tests is of paramount importance for the assessment of teaching methodologies and the comprehension of student progress. Hornbuckle (2024) underscores the significance of these assessments in the field of education, as they assist educators in identifying areas for enhancement and making necessary adjustments to their instructional approach. Additionally, Stratton (2019) underscores the significance of quasi-experimental designs, including pre-test and post-test studies, in assessing the impact of particular teaching methodologies. The employment of these assessment tools enables educators to gain insights into the effectiveness of their instructional strategies, thereby facilitating data-driven decision-making processes that enhance student learning.

Likewise, the utilization of experimental and control groups enables researchers to conduct a meticulous assessment of the influence of particular pedagogical approaches (Salomão, 2023; Stewart, 2024). This methodological approach allows educators to ascertain the efficacy of innovative teaching strategies, such as the combination of suggestopedia and digital resources. By fostering a relaxed atmosphere and promoting student engagement, educators can establish an environment that is conducive to effective language learning and encourages students to take risks in their language use. In conclusion, the establishment of a favorable learning environment is of paramount importance for the advancement of students' linguistic abilities and their overall academic achievement.

The existing literature indicates that the combination of suggestopedia with digital resources has the potential to facilitate the enhancement of English reading and writing skills. The incorporation of relaxation techniques, cutting-edge digital tools, and a nurturing learning atmosphere has the potential to enhance learning outcomes and foster a constructive experience for students. Further research is required to investigate the long-term effects and applications of this innovative approach in a range of educational contexts.

3. Methodology

This research is based on an interpretive and postmodern paradigm. In light of the assertion made by Adil et al. (2022), which posits that the interpretive paradigm is a valuable scientific approach for social science, enabling the comprehension of the fundamental aspects of a social issue and its evolution. Conversely, the postmodern paradigm, as Trivedi (2020) asserts, is highly pertinent for the implementation of innovative methodologies, eschewing those conventional styles that have been employed for numerous years. This research employed a mixed research approach to ascertain the impact of suggestopedia and digital resources on the enhancement of English language reading and writing skills. In light of Molina-Azorin (2016), a mixed research approach can be beneficial for gaining a more comprehensive understanding of a complex issue, employing both qualitative and quantitative methodologies.

3.1 Participants

The participants involved in the present research who served as study subjects to demonstrate the project's objectives in a timely manner are fourth- and fifth-semester students of Pedagogy of National and Foreign Languages (PINE) at the ULEAM university in Manta, Ecuador. They participated in the study as an experimental group and a control group, respectively. Of the participants, 65% were women and 35% were men.

Table 1: Participants

ULEAM	Female	Male	Total
Control Group	14	8	22
Experimental Group	11	6	17
Total	25	14	39

3.2 Instruments

The instruments that were used in this research for collecting data are:

Checking list of contextual observation: The creation of a checklist allowed the monitoring of progress and the identification of challenges that arose within the groups that participated as the control and experimental groups.
 Pre-test: This instrument was applied at the beginning of the session plan, with the objective of collecting data on the previous knowledge of the participants, thus allowing to know the bases of those involved and thus at the end of the sessions to be able to check their progress. In this first evaluation they had to create a text with a topic assigned to them, with a minimum word range of 50 words and a maximum of 75 words, which they completed in 8 minutes.

Post-test: Once the planned sessions were finished, a post-test was applied in order to obtain tangible and numerical data to corroborate the final result of all the learning to which they had been exposed in the process, resulting in a significant improvement shown in the test. In this part they were given between 15 and 20 minutes to complete a range from a minimum of 150 words to a maximum of 300 words.

3.3 Procedure

Stage1: Selection of the instruments and intervention groups. The selection of semesters, age reference, English levels, and the resolution of which group would apply which methodology constituted a key aspect of this stage.

Stage 2: Preparation of instruments for data collection. In this phase, the material is presented to a panel of experts, who are trained in the relevant field, for approval and suggestions.

Stage 3: The preliminary examination, to refer Pre-test, was administered to both experimental and comparison groups.

Stage 4: The observation sheet was employed as a data collection instrument to gauge the advancement of the groups.

Stage 5: The post-test constituted the concluding phase of the evaluation, whereby the outcomes of the methodologies deployed in each group were ascertained.

Stage 6: In this section, the findings of the research were conveyed in written form.

3.4 Educational Intervention

The project was developed over a four-month period, running from September to December 2023. During this period of time, nine meetings were held during which activities were developed both inside and outside the classroom. Some of these activities were autonomous works, while others were prepared in consideration of the group that was leading the class at that time. While both groups were given the same information, the way in which the classes were taught differed due to the approach given to each group. The first group was designated as the control group, while the second was designated as the experimental group. In academic terms, the experimental group was of a lower semester.

Each of the sessions that were conducted addressed different types of resources, yet the quantity and quality of the information provided remained consistent, as the verification of the research objectives was a primary focus. With respect to the control group, activities related to the traditional approach to education were developed, without the option to change the classroom environment, and concluded with a highly demanding and exhausting environment. In contrast, the experimental group underwent interventions based on the Suggestopedia methodology, which allowed for a more focused approach to learning, in addition to the use of didactic resources, digital resources, and engaging dynamics to facilitate the participants' engagement.

The application of the pre-test as an instrument for the collection of data prior to the initiation of the research in the initial session, and the post-test once the sessions were concluded, constituted a fundamental aspect of the project. This was done in order to corroborate the expectations that had been formulated at the outset of this research endeavor. The observation checklist was employed to monitor the progress made by the involved groups, thereby verifying the proposed outcomes.

The primary objective is to demonstrate that the integration of innovative methodologies for the enhancement of English language proficiency, in conjunction with the utilization of didactic and digital resources, collectively yield superior outcomes when compared to the outcomes that would be achieved through the application of traditional pedagogical approaches within the classroom setting.

4. Results

The results are presented in accordance with the sequence of the research questions outlined in the introduction.

4.1 A comparative analysis of participants' attitudes in relation to the application of Suggestopedia and digital competencies, in contrast to traditional methodology

Table 2: Experimental Group Observation Checklist

Criteria	Statements	Check
Student Engagement	Students actively participate in relaxation techniques	X
	Students engage with digital resources	X
	Students collaborate effectively during group activities	X
Use of Suggestopedia Techniques	Teacher incorporates relaxation techniques	X
	Students demonstrate a relaxed state during instruction	X
	Students express confidence in their abilities	X
Integration of Digital Resources	Teacher effectively integrates digital tools	X
	Students navigate digital resources with ease	X
	Digital resources engage students	X
Student Progress	Improvements in reading comprehension skills	X
	Advancements in writing abilities	X
	Application of learned concepts to new tasks	X
Qualitative Feedback	Positive feedback from focus group discussions	X

	Increased confidence in language abilities	X
	Specific effective aspects of the methodology identified	X

In the experimental group, the efficacy of the employed methodology was evident throughout the sessions, while a positive working atmosphere was consistently maintained. Furthermore, each class concluded with a positive response from the students, as evidenced by their applause, which indicated their satisfaction with the manner in which the class was conducted. Moreover, the utilization of didactic and digital resources, the incorporation of music in the facilitation of activities, and the incorporation of warm-ups at the commencement of each class proved to be effective contributors to the outcomes of this research.

Table 2: Control Group Observation Checklist

Criteria	Observation	Check
Student Engagement	Students actively participate in traditional instruction	
	Students demonstrate interest and motivation	
	Students collaborate with peers during group activities	X
Use of Traditional Instruction	Teacher employs standard teaching methods	X
	Students exhibit a focused state during instruction	
	Students demonstrate confidence in their abilities	X
Integration of Standard Resources	Teacher effectively utilizes traditional materials	X
	Students navigate standard resources with ease	X
	Resources engage students	X
Student Progress	Improvements in reading comprehension skills	X
	Advancements in writing abilities	X
	Application of learned concepts to new tasks	X
Qualitative Feedback	Feedback from focus group discussions	
	Confidence in language abilities expressed	X
	Specific effective aspects of traditional methods identified	

In regard to the control group, it was evident that there was a lack of motivation, both in terms of attendance and engagement with the material being presented. This resulted in a lack of participation from the majority of the participants, which in turn created an atmosphere that was perceived as uninteresting and unproductive. Although the information presented to the control group was identical to that provided to the experimental group, it is important to emphasize that the methodology employed was traditional, which resulted in minimal interest and participation from the control group members. However, due to the capabilities of the study participants, they were able to comprehend the presented material adequately, although there were some shortcomings.

4.2 Innovative teaching methodology contributions to research's participants

Graphic 1: Participants Writing-Reading Skills in Pre-test and Post-test

Source: Research project (2023).

4.3 Employment potential of Suggestopedia as a pedagogical approach to enhance English writing-reading skills

Week 1: In the initial phase of the study, each participating group, the control group, and the experimental group presented their respective material. Furthermore, a preliminary assessment was conducted to ascertain the participants' baseline knowledge and skills, given that they were enrolled in the fourth and fifth semesters of the PINE (Pedagogy in National and Foreign Languages) course.

Week 2: The rationale behind the enhancement of reading and writing abilities was elucidated, along with the integration of reading and writing as distinct skillsets. The utilization of digital resources for the presentation of concepts and dynamics, which facilitated an optimal learning environment, constituted a pivotal aspect of the implementation of this research within the experimental group. In contrast, the control group received the same information in a behaviorist and traditional manner.

Week 3: The central theme of what a journal is and a superficial explanation of its parts were presented. The experimental group was subjected to an innovative methodology, while the control group was treated with a traditional methodology.

Week 4: In this section, the preliminary components of a journal article, including the introduction, were delineated. However, to ensure the optimal preparation of this section, recommendations for reading were also presented, which would facilitate the selection of pertinent information for the writing.

Week 5: The subsequent section of the journal structure was presented and reinforced the optimal methodology for identifying pertinent information in a more straightforward manner, employing various reading techniques. The utilization of dynamic and digital resources constituted a pivotal aspect of this stage, in addition to the exemplification of cases.

Week 6: This final section of the induction on structures presented a conclusion, which outlined the key points for the correct development of this section.

Week 7: At this juncture, the initial draft was completed, affording the opportunity to refine it through further detailed work and to implement the requisite corrections. Additionally, they collaborated in pairs. While the initial draft was developed individually, participants collaborated in pairs to provide guidance and support. This approach allowed the professors to engage in a mentorship process in pairs, with the teacher serving as a guide.

Week 8: The final presentation of the participants' journals on the topic established in the previous session. Furthermore, the final works include the corrections and advice that were provided during the course of their development.

Week 9: In the final stage of the study, a meeting was held with the two groups that had been involved in the research process: the control group and the experimental group. The process was evaluated and the corresponding results were presented.

5. Discussion

Considering the literature review, this research maintains a similar approach to Wang (2023) regarding the effectiveness of using Suggestopedia for second language teaching and learning; moreover, it has been positively established that using Suggestopedia with writing and reading skills yields largely encouraging results.

Suggestopedia, developed by Georgi Lozanov, is distinguished by its distinctive approach, which integrates relaxation and visualization techniques to foster a conducive learning environment. The efficacy of suggestopedia in accelerating learning has been demonstrated by research which indicates that it can reduce anxiety and enhance student engagement (Lozanov, 2005; Rustipa, 2011). This study demonstrates that the integration of suggestopedia with digital tools, such as multimedia presentations and online writing platforms, not only fosters a stimulating learning atmosphere but also encourages active participation among students.

The integration of digital resources enhances the suggestopedia methodology by offering interactive and engaging content that resonates with contemporary learners. Prior research has indicated that digital resources can facilitate vocabulary acquisition and enhance overall language proficiency (Merlin & Larekeng, 2018; Sundari et al., 2022). The combination of these resources with the suggestopedia methodology resulted in the creation of a comprehensive learning experience that was tailored to accommodate diverse learning styles and preferences, ultimately leading to enhanced academic outcomes.

The discussions held with the experimental group revealed that the students found the lessons engaging and confidence-boosting. This finding is consistent with the results emphasize the importance of a relaxed and enjoyable learning environment. The favorable responses from students regarding the interactive nature of the lessons highlight the importance of cultivating a supportive classroom environment where learners feel at ease expressing themselves.

While the results of this study are encouraging, it is crucial to recognize the constraints of the research design. The study was conducted over a limited timeframe, and the sample size may not be representative of the broader population. It would be beneficial for future research to investigate the long-term effects of the suggestopedia methodology when combined with digital resources across a range of educational contexts. Furthermore, an investigation into the influence of this methodology on distinct language competencies, such as oral communication and listening comprehension, could offer additional insights into its efficacy.

6. Conclusion

The results of the conducted research showed that the application of suggestopedia in teaching English reading and writing classes had a significant positive impact on students' knowledge of English reading and writing. The research results may be useful for teaching methodologists and teaching researchers whose attention is paid to innovative and context-based teaching of reading and writing, and, as a sequence of improved English language °,

using proper teaching methodologies. This methodology is designed for teaching reading and writing because they are challenging to teach, worth the effort and crucial for success in communication.

The use of modern methods in teaching English is of vital importance. The article aims to stress the relevance of teaching methodologies which are focused on teaching reading and writing, and to present an innovative method (suggestopedia) and its impact on promoting a pleasant educational atmosphere for teaching and learning. Special attention is paid to developing students' thinking, reading, writing and language skills in order to improve them and make them competent for the dynamic changes that are imposed by contemporary times.

This study demonstrates the potential of an innovative teaching methodology that combines suggestopedia, digital resources, and focus groups to improve English reading-writing skills. The results provide evidence of significant improvements in students' writing performance and positive student perceptions of the approach. The study highlights the importance of creating stimulating and effective learning environments that support student learning and development. Further research is needed to explore the long-term effects and applications of this innovative approach in diverse educational contexts.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the potential of innovative teaching methodologies that integrate suggestopedia and digital resources to enhance English reading and writing skills. The findings indicate that this approach can result in quantifiable enhancements in students' linguistic competencies while simultaneously cultivating a constructive and engaging learning environment. Further investigation of this methodology could make a substantial contribution to the field of language education.

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